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Development of a Low-Cost Ultrasound Flow Sensor

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

- ADC Analog to Digital
- AFE Analog Front End
- GHG Greenhouse gas
- ITMOs Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes
- LNA Low Noise Amplifier
- NDCs Nationally determined contributions
- PCB Printed Circuit Board
- PGA Programmable Gain Amplifier
- RRMSE Relative Root Mean Square Error
- RTD Resistance Temperature Detectors
- SNR Signal to Noise Ratio
- SPI Serial Peripheral Interface
- TDC Time to Digital

ABSTRACT

Accurate monitoring of emission reduction projects is essential to ensure the environmental integrity of carbon crediting mechanisms established under the Paris Agreement. In biodigester-based clean cooking projects, monitoring is often based on survey data, which is prone to systematic overestimation and may lead to over-crediting. Direct measurement of biodigester usage through low-cost sensing offers a promising alternative; however, existing gas flow and composition sensors are typically too expensive for large-scale deployment in decentralized settings.

This thesis presents the design, implementation, and evaluation of a low-cost transit-time ultrasonic flow meter intended for biogas applications. The proposed sensor measures volumetric flow rate and estimates gas composition by combining bidirectional ultrasonic time-of-flight. The system integrates commercially available components on a custom printed circuit board and is calibrated using controlled air and CH₄-CO₂ gas mixtures representative of field conditions.

Experimental results demonstrate that, for air, the sensor achieves a mean relative error below 3 % over a flow range of 2–10 Lmin⁻¹. For biogas-like mixtures with methane concentrations between 70 % and 100 %, gas composition can be estimated with a mean relative error below 1 %, while volumetric flow rate errors increase substantially due to ultrasonic signal attenuation in CO₂-rich environments. At methane concentrations below 70 %, reliable measurements are not achievable with the adopted architecture. The total estimated production cost of the prototype is approximately 36 CHF, significantly lower than that of commercially available ultrasonic flow meters.

The results highlight both the potential and the limitations of low-cost transit-time ultrasonic sensing for biogas monitoring. While the proposed sensor is suitable for applications involving high methane concentrations, extending its operational range to CO₂-rich mixtures will require more advanced signal acquisition and processing techniques. Future work should therefore focus on ADC-based ultrasonic measurement approaches that offer improved robustness under low signal-to-noise conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Climate change is widely regarded as one of the defining challenges of the 21st century. Addressing it requires coordinated international action and transparent accounting frameworks, which are established under the Paris Agreement. Within this framework, countries may contribute either by reducing emissions domestically or by financing mitigation projects abroad and transferring the resulting mitigation outcomes through carbon crediting mechanisms. These financial flows are typically directed from developed to developing countries, where they support both emission reductions and local development. A persistent challenge within this system is the accurate quantification of achieved emission reductions. In many cases, monitoring relies on survey-based approaches, which are prone to systematic overestimation due to reporting biases. This issue is common for biogas-based projects, which convert organic waste into biogas and play an important role in enabling the transition to clean cooking solutions. To ensure the integrity of carbon crediting schemes and to limit over-crediting, an alternative to survey-based monitoring is required. One promising approach consists in directly measuring biogas usage through a sensor capable of quantifying biogas flow and composition. For such a solution to be deployable at scale, it must combine sufficient measurement accuracy with low production cost and minimal maintenance requirements.

1.1 Paris Agreement

The Paris Agreement is a legally binding international treaty that was adopted by nearly 200 countries in 2015. The ambitious goal of the agreement is to keep the increase in global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels. Ideally, the temperature increase should be limited to 1.5°C, as defined in art. 2 of the Agreement ([UNFCCC, 2015](#)). This objective implies that [Greenhouse gas \(GHG\)](#) emissions should peak before 2025 and be reduced by 43 % by 2030.

Signatory governments are mandated to specify their contributions towards the achievement of the Agreement's goals through [Nationally determined contributions \(NDCs\)](#). NDCs are defined every five years and are required to become progressively more ambitious at each

iteration, in accordance with the principle of progression. To support Parties in the formulation of successive [NDCs](#) and to ensure transparency, Parties are required to regularly report on their progress. This information is subsequently aggregated within the Global Stocktake, which assesses collective progress towards the long-term objectives of the Agreement and helps identify remaining gaps. The results of the first Global Stocktake were presented at COP28 in 2023.

Article 6 of the treaty lays the foundations for bilateral or multilateral cooperation among participants, it enables cost-effective climate action through international cooperation and market mechanisms. Paragraph 6.2 defines how participants must track and report the mitigation outcomes that are transferred for the purpose of achieving [NDCs](#) with particular emphasis placed on avoiding the double counting of mitigation outcomes. Paragraph 6.4, meanwhile, introduces a mechanism for the exchange of carbon credits that is supervised by an international body. The implementation of Article 6 mechanisms has been widely debated due to concerns related to environmental integrity, double counting, and the robustness of monitoring, reporting and verification frameworks ([Schneider & La Hoz Theuer, 2019](#)).

Switzerland is disproportionately affected by climate change. While the global mean temperature increase relative to pre-industrial levels is approximately +1.3 °C, the corresponding increase in Switzerland reached +2.9 °C in 2024 ([MeteoSwiss & ETH Zurich, 2025](#)). The Swiss population is already experiencing the impacts of climate change: extreme heat waves, more intense precipitation, and reduced snowfall are becoming increasingly common.

Switzerland joined the Paris Agreement in October 2017. The treaty's goals are implemented through the Climate and Innovation Act and the CO₂ Act, which were both accepted by the population. [Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes \(ITMOs\)](#) are part of the Swiss strategy to reduce the carbon footprint, and multiple projects are already ongoing abroad.

These commitments motivate Switzerland's participation in international mitigation projects based on decentralized biodigesters, such as the Malawi biodigester program considered in this thesis.

1.2 Clean Cooking

Worldwide, more than two billion people rely on inefficient open-fire cooking systems fueled by firewood, livestock manure, or charcoal. These individuals inhale daily toxic smoke, which contributes to approximately 3 million premature deaths annually related to indoor air pollution. Women are typically responsible for fuel collection and cooking—time-consuming activities that limit participation in income-generating work. Although the global situation has improved over the past 20 years, this has not been the case in sub-Saharan Africa, where conditions have worsened. In sub-Saharan Africa, indoor air pollution is considered the second

leading single cause for premature deaths (IEA, 2025). Traditional cooking methods not only have a social impact, but also contribute to climate change. As combustion is not controlled, heat can escape into the environment, meaning that more biomass is required. It is estimated that up to 34 % of the firewood used in traditional cooking is unsustainably harvested, leading to deforestation and possibly desertification. Up to 50 % of black carbon emissions are related to household combustion, and the conversion to fuel-efficient cooking methods could decrease these emissions by 30 – 60 % (Clean Cooking Alliance, 2023). To tackle this problem, cheap and more efficient fuels are required.

1.3 Biodigesters and Biogas

Biogas constitutes a promising alternative cooking fuel and is produced through a process called anaerobic digestion, during which microorganisms decompose organic waste in the absence of oxygen to generate mainly methane and carbon dioxide. The reaction generates trace amounts of water vapor, ammonia (NH₃) and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), which is highly corrosive to metals therefore limits the sensor choice. A by-product of anaerobic digestion is called digestate, which may be used as a natural fertilizer (Koszel & Lorencowicz, 2015). The content of methane in biogas ranges from 49.5 to 70.5 % (Li *et al.*, 2019), and it depends on multiple factors like origin of organic matter, temperature and reaction time. A biodigester is engineered to optimize the conditions for anaerobic digestion, and trap the biogas produced. Methane has an estimated global warming potential approximately 25 times higher than CO₂, biodigesters not only provide fuel for clean cooking, but they also prevent the release of GHG from organic waste in the atmosphere.

Switzerland and Malawi are working together on a project to provide dairy farmers with household biodigesters. The biodigesters are used to transform organic waste from the cows to biogas. The biogas is finally used to replace biomass as fuel source for cooking (KliK, 2023).

1.4 Flow Sensors

As defined in Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, mitigation outcomes must be accounted for in a transparent and accurate manner. To account for mitigation outcomes from biodigesters, international standards such as the Gold Standard are used, which typically rely on questionnaires (Gold Standard, 2023). Unfortunately, survey participants tend to overestimate the actual use of biodigesters, which results in an accounting of mitigation outcomes that exceeds the real quantity (Gill-Wiehl *et al.*, 2024), a phenomenon known as over-crediting. A sensor capable of measuring the amount of methane used would lead to a more rigorous allocation of

mitigation outcomes.

In addition to flow quantification, biogas composition measurements provide critical information regarding anaerobic digestion efficiency. Many factors influence the operating conditions of the biodigester (Nsair *et al.*, 2020), and the composition of the biogas can serve as an alarm if it falls below a predefined threshold.

Some commercially available sensors exist, but they are prohibitively expensive and usually intended for larger biogas production plants (KROHNE Messtechnik GmbH, 2025). Only one device is specifically designed for household biodigesters, the Smart Biogas from InclusiveEnergy (Smart Biogas, 2025); the company was recently acquired by Sistema.bio, a company focused on developing biodigester technology, effectively creating a near-monopoly. To fill this gap, recent research at GHE identified transit-time flow meters as a potential solution thanks to high accuracy, components low-cost and low-power consumption, ideal for remote applications. Oya *et al.* (2022) developed an air flow measurement sensor based on the MSP430FR6043 from Texas Instruments able to achieve an accuracy of 0.33% between 1440-1600 Lh⁻¹ while Chen *et al.* (2020) obtained an accuracy of 1.09% over the same flow rate range using a TDC-GP22 from ScioSense. Joos *et al.* (1993) developed a sensor to measure the composition of binary gas mixtures with an error below 2% for a mixture of CO₂ and air.

1.5 Justification and Research Questions

To ensure a fair mitigation outcomes market that limits the phenomenon of over-crediting, it is necessary to move from a questionnaire-based system to one based on real data. This can be achieved by using a network of sensors that collect information on the usage of biodigesters. These sensors must be accurate, and at the same time very low-cost, in order to create the widest possible network. Finally, the household biogas sensor market remains small and the risk of monopoly is very high; for this reason, it is of fundamental importance to develop an open-source alternative capable of competing with much more expensive devices.

1.5.1 Research Questions

Considering the previously described motivations, the following research question was defined:

- Can an ultrasound flow sensor be developed at a low-cost (< 100 CHF) and achieve high accuracy (< 3% error)?

2 METHODS

The development of the sensor is divided into four main areas: electronics, mechanics, data processing, and calibration. In each of these categories, the objective is to maximize measurement accuracy and repeatability; in particular, in the electronics domain, significant emphasis is placed on identifying the best trade-off between component cost and accuracy.

2.1 Principle of Operation

This section introduces the concept employed by a transit time flow meter, as well as the derivation of the equations used to obtain the volumetric flow and the gas composition.

2.1.1 Transit Time Flow Measurement Theory

Ultrasonic flow meters are commonly divided into two categories: transit-time flow meters and Doppler effect flow meters. In this work, a transit-time sensor is developed, as this technology is better suited for applications with clean fluids. Systems based on the Doppler effect are more appropriate for turbid fluids (e.g. blood), that is, fluids containing scatterers capable of reflecting ultrasound waves (Wang *et al.*, 2021). In transit-time flow meters, an ultrasonic signal propagates between two transducers across the flow as depicted in Figure 2.1. A timing circuit measures the time elapsed between transmission and reception. The signal traveling from transducer P_1 to transducer P_2 propagates in the direction of the flow (downstream propagation), while the signal traveling in the opposite direction propagates against the direction of the flow (upstream propagation). As a result, the upstream and downstream signals exhibit different transit times, this difference is defined as Δ_{TOF} .

2.1.2 Volumetric Flow Rate & Composition Computation

The propagation velocity in the two directions is given by the linear combination of the flow velocity v and the speed of sound c , which depends on the medium. Exploiting this consideration, it is possible to derive the equations for the propagation velocities u_{down} and u_{up} :

Figure 2.1. Sketch of sensor housing with dimensional parameters.

$$u_{\text{down}} = \frac{L}{T_{\text{down}}} = c + v \cos(\theta) \quad (2.1)$$

$$u_{\text{up}} = \frac{L}{T_{\text{up}}} = c - v \cos(\theta) \quad (2.2)$$

where L is the distance traveled by the ultrasonic signal and θ is its angle of incidence, both of which depend on the design of the sensor housing and are therefore known. The unknowns are v , the flow velocity, and the speed of sound c . The transit times T_{down} and T_{up} are measured in the downstream and upstream directions, respectively. Because c is significantly larger than v , the transit time difference is in the nanosecond scale. By combining Eqs. 2.1–2.2 and rearranging in terms of T_{down} and T_{up} , the unknowns can be obtained as:

$$v = \frac{L}{2 \cos(\theta)} \frac{T_{\text{up}} - T_{\text{down}}}{T_{\text{down}} T_{\text{down}}} \quad (2.3)$$

$$c = \frac{L}{2} \frac{T_{\text{up}} + T_{\text{down}}}{T_{\text{up}} T_{\text{down}}} \quad (2.4)$$

Finally, the average flow velocity can then be used to determine the volumetric flow rate Q :

$$Q = v \cdot A \quad (2.5)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area, which depends again on the sensor housing design and is therefore known. By measuring the volumetric flow over time, it is possible to estimate the volume of biogas being consumed.

For ideal gas mixtures, the speed of sound is defined as:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\text{mix}}RT}{M_{\text{mix}}}} \quad (2.6)$$

where γ_{mix} is the specific heat ratio of the mixture, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature and M_{mix} is the molar mass of the mixture. In a binary gas mixture, the heat capacity ratio and the molar mass could be rewritten as:

$$\gamma_{\text{mix}} = \frac{x_1c_{p,1} + x_2c_{p,2}}{x_1c_{v,1} + x_2c_{v,2}} \quad (2.7)$$

$$M_{\text{mix}} = x_1M_1 + x_2M_2 \quad (2.8)$$

where $c_{p,i}$ and $c_{v,i}$ are the molar heat capacities, M_i is the molar mass and x_i is the mole fraction. In a binary gas mixture, x_2 could be rewritten as $x_2 = 1 - x_1$ meaning that Eq. 2.6 could be rewritten as a function of x_1 . As Eq. 2.6 is not invertible, an iterative approach is required to obtain x_1 . A simpler method based on linear interpolation could be used instead: look-up tables can be generated for binary $\text{CH}_4 - \text{CO}_2$ mixtures that map c to methane concentration. This is achieved using the CoolProp library, which can generate mixture properties based on high-accuracy Helmholtz energy formulations (Bell *et al.*, 2014). The look-up tables are generated by first measuring temperature and then querying CoolProp for the speed of sound across methane concentrations from 0 to 100% at an assumed constant pressure. The composition can then be determined by interpolation:

$$x(c_{\text{meas}}) = x_i + \frac{c_{\text{meas}} - c_i}{c_{i+1} - c_i} (x_{i+1} - x_i), \quad c_i \leq c_{\text{meas}} \leq c_{i+1}. \quad (2.9)$$

where c is the speed of sound and x is the concentration of methane. An example of a look-up table is shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2. Methane percentage vs. speed of sound for CH₄ – CO₂ gas mixture, at standard conditions.

Referring to a mixture of CO₂ and air, [Joos et al. \(1993\)](#) report that temperature measurement errors have a much larger impact than pressure measurement errors. A variation of 100 mbar causes a change in the speed of sound of less than 0.01%, whereas an error of 1°C results in a concentration error of 0.7%. Accurate temperature measurement is therefore critical.

2.2 Electronics

This section describes the main electronic components of the sensor. The system is based on a combination of a [Time to Digital \(TDC\)](#) chip and an [Analog Front End \(AFE\)](#) chip from Texas Instruments used to drive the ultrasonic transducers. An additional amplifier is included on the transmission side to increase signal power for propagation in highly attenuating media. An ESP32 microcontroller performs data processing and controls the peripheral components. All electronics are integrated on a custom [Printed Circuit Board \(PCB\)](#), a rendering of the PCB is shown in [Figure 2.3](#). A flowchart demonstrating how the components interact is provided in the [Appendix A.2](#).

Figure 2.3. Rendering of the custom PCB.

2.2.1 Microcontroller

The microcontroller communicates with peripheral devices via the [Serial Peripheral Interface \(SPI\)](#) standard, it is responsible for the correct configuration of the peripherals after start-up and takes care of mathematical operations: time-of-flight calculation, temperature calculation, data filtering, conversion to volumetric flow and composition. The ESP32, a microcontroller developed by Espressif, was selected. The ESP32 operates at 3.3 V, which allows it to interface with peripherals without the need to include a logic level shifter to adapt the signal voltage levels. The ESP32 is low-cost, easy to use, and is supported by a wide range of development kits, which reduces prototyping time. For this project, the ESP32-DevKitC was used ([Espressif Systems, 2025](#)).

2.2.2 Timing Chip & Analog Front End

Since the sensor measures the time elapsed between the transmission and reception of a signal, it is essential to employ a component capable of measuring time intervals as short as a few nanoseconds with high precision, as a 1 nanosecond error would result in a difference in volumetric flow of $\pm 0.1 \text{ L min}^{-1}$. Transit-time flow meters typically rely on two timing approaches: [TDC](#), which uses a combination of threshold and zero-crossing techniques, and [Analog to Digital \(ADC\)](#), which is based on analog-to-digital signal acquisition. [ADC](#)-based systems typically achieve higher accuracy due to more advanced time-estimation methods and are generally more robust to noise. In [Table 2.1](#), three alternatives are compared: They differ primarily in their timing approach, cost and built-in amplification. As cost-effectiveness of the sensor is fundamental, the evaluation was based primarily on the trade-off between price and accuracy.

Table 2.1. Timing chips comparison.

Model	Tech- nology	Cost [CHF]	Single-shot uncertainty [ps] ¹	Amplification
TDC7200 + TDC1000	TDC	4.68	50 at 100 μ s	5.5 V TX signal, up to 41 dB gain for rx signal.
GP22	TDC	5.98	39 – 70	Does not include amplification of rx signal.
MSP430FR6043	ADC	5.52 – 12.03	250	3.3 V TX signal, up to 30 dB gain for rx signal, CIC filter.

¹ GP22 and TDC7200 publish σ for the internal time-measurement circuit. MSP430FR6043 publishes system-level differential time-of-flight (dToF) performance from the complete ultrasonic sensing chain; an internal-only σ is not specified in the datasheet. System-level σ includes analog front-end, transducer, and propagation effects and is therefore significantly larger than the internal TDC σ .

The MSP430FR6043 uses [ADC](#), achieving the highest accuracy but costs more than the other alternatives. At 40 Lmin⁻¹, the GP22 exhibits a slightly lower error (1.67%) than the MSP430FR6043 (2.04%) ([Oya et al., 2022](#)). Based on considerations of cost, ease of integration, and prior laboratory testing, the Texas Instruments TDC7200 and TDC1000 combination was selected. The TDC7200 is dedicated to measuring the interval between a START signal and one or multiple STOP signals; these signals are generated by the TDC1000, known as an [AFE](#), which is required to interface the timer with the transducers.

The [TDC](#) method uses a state machine to evaluate the echo signal and generate a stop signal for the timing chip. The received signal is compared with a reference voltage V_{REF} , when the difference between the two falls below a threshold V_{THLD} , the threshold detect comparator notifies the event manager to consider the next zero crossing as valid. When the received signal crosses the reference voltage V_{REF} the zero-cross detect comparator notifies the event manager, which generates STOP signals until the number of received events NUM_RX is reached. An example with $NUM_RX = 3$ is shown in [Figure 2.4](#).

The [AFE](#) performs two main functions: the first is to generate the square wave sent to the transmitting transducer while simultaneously generating a START signal for the timer; the second is to convert the signal received from the receiving transducer into a STOP signal, amplifying it if necessary. The interaction between TDC7200 and TDC1000 is represented in [Figure A.1](#), available in the Appendix. The TDC1000 allows a transmission of up to 32 pulses and amplification of the received signal up to 41 dB; moreover, it supports the connection of up to two [Resistance Temperature Detectors \(RTD\)](#), thereby facilitating temperature measurement,

Figure 2.4. Stop signal generation: the event manager generates a stop signal when two conditions are met (1) threshold detect comparator notifies event manager, (2) zero-cross detect comparator notifies event manager.

a key parameter for determining the composition of the fluid.

Both chips provide extensive configuration flexibility through programmable register settings, which are tiny storage locations where 1 byte of data is stored. By modifying the register values, it is possible to define how the chip behaves, for example by defining which amplifiers should be active, and how much gain they provide, or by defining the number of pulses that the AFE should generate. The final register values were determined through an iterative tuning process aimed at achieving stable echo detection and maximizing the signal-to-noise ratio. The selected configurations are reported in Tables A.1 and A.2 in the Appendix.

2.2.3 Filtering & Amplification

The signal, particularly when propagating through a gas, is significantly attenuated. This attenuation depends on two main factors: transmission losses going from one medium to another (transducer–gas) and propagation losses within the gas itself. To mitigate this attenuation, either the transmitted signal can be amplified or additional gain can be applied to the received signal.

A Texas Instruments UCC2753x single-gate driver was added to the transmit path. This driver allows the signal generated by the AFE to be amplified to a voltage range between 10 and 35 V, which results in a significant increase in the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). This driver was selected as it is able to amplify fast switching signals without affecting the rising edge of the wave. Operational amplifiers that offer a high slew rate are significantly more expensive, as the OPA552 from Texas Instruments, which has a slew rate of $24 \text{ V } \mu\text{s}^{-1}$ but costs almost 4 times the selected gate driver.

On the receiving side, as described in Section 2.2.2, the AFE allows the received signal to be amplified by up to 41 dB; this is achieved through a **Low Noise Amplifier (LNA)**, which provides approximately 20 dB of gain, and a **Programmable Gain Amplifier (PGA)**, which allows the gain to be set between 0 and 21 dB. Each amplifier can be individually activated.

By reducing the noise on the received signal, it is possible to lower the voltage threshold which the signal needs to cross to qualify for a stop signal generation. To reduce noise, first-order filters were placed between the amplification stages. These filters consist of a resistor and a capacitor, whose values depend on the desired cutoff frequency, which in turn is determined by the type of transducer used. Specifically, a low-pass filter is implemented between LNAOUT and PGAIN, and a high-pass filter between PGAOUT and COMPIN, as shown in Figure 2.5. A low-pass filter attenuates frequencies above the cutoff frequency, while a high-pass filter

Figure 2.5. First-order RC filters used for signal conditioning.

attenuates frequencies below it. The cutoff frequency, expressed in Hz, is calculated as follows:

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi RC} \tag{2.10}$$

where R is the resistance value in Ω and C is the capacitance value in F. The component values reported in Table 2.2 were selected according to the resonance frequency of the transducers.

Table 2.2. RC filter component.

Resonance frequency	R_1	C_1	$f_{c,LP}$	R_2	C_2	$f_{c,HP}$
500 kHz	100 Ω	2.7 nF	589.4 kHz	5.1 k Ω	68 pF	458.9 kHz

2.2.4 Transducers

The transducers used in the sensor exploit the piezoelectric effect to convert an electrical signal into acoustic pressure and vice versa. The key parameter in transducer selection is the resonant frequency. In fact, for gas applications the ideal frequency is on the order of hundreds

of kHz. The attenuation coefficient of acoustic waves is directly proportional to frequency and depends on humidity, temperature and pressure. It is defined by the Beer-Lambert Law:

$$p = p_0 e^{-\alpha l} \quad (2.11)$$

Where p is the acoustic pressure on the receiver side, p_0 is the acoustic pressure at the source, α is the attenuation coefficient and l is the distance between receiver and source. An overview of the attenuation coefficients for the gases considered in this work is provided in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3. Attenuation coefficients for gases at 200 kHz (Franco *et al.*, 2025; Harper *et al.*, 2009; Jakevicius & Demcenko, 2008).

Medium	α (m ⁻¹)
Air (40% humidity)	8
CH ₄	12.3 – 14
CO ₂	42.6 – 69

The transducers employed in the sensor are manufactured by Jiakang Electronics Co., a partner company of Texas Instruments and recommended in the TDC7200 documentation. For gas applications the 500 kHz model was chosen, as it provided higher signal-to-noise ratio in comparison to the 200 kHz model. Since the characteristics of piezoelectric transducers depend on manufacturing process, transducers are supplied in matched pairs originating from the same production batch to minimize impedance deviation. Two transducer pairs were evaluated by recording the zero-flow transit-time difference Δt_{TOF} over 200 consecutive measurements. This is the time difference measured when flow speed is zero, and it is expected to be close to zero. Figure 2.6 shows the demeaned Δt_{TOF} sequences, while Table 2.4 reports the corresponding mean and standard deviation.

Table 2.4. Comparison transducer pairs

Transducer pair	Resonant Frequency (kHz)	Mean (ns)	Standard Deviation (ns)
Pair 1	500	20.97	1.351
Pair 2	500	26.07	2.753

2.3 Mechanical Design

2.3.1 Inline vs. Clamp-on configuration

Commercial ultrasonic flow meters are available in two configurations: inline and clamp-on. In the inline configuration, a section of pipe is removed to install the sensor, and the transducers

Figure 2.6. Demeaned zero-flow transit-time differences Δt_{TOF} for two transducer pairs over 200 consecutive measurements.

are in direct contact with the fluid. In the clamp-on configuration, the pipe remains intact and the transducers are mounted on its outer surface. This second configuration is preferable for temporary measurements or in cases where it is not possible to interrupt the flow during installation, due to its non-invasive nature. However, it is not suitable for all fluids: ultrasonic signals are strongly attenuated when transmitted between two media, particularly when one of them is a gas. The proportion of the ultrasonic energy transmitted depends on the acoustic impedance of the media, as shown by the following equation:

$$T_{AB} = \frac{4Z_A Z_B}{(Z_A + Z_B)^2} \quad (2.12)$$

where Z_A and Z_B are the acoustic impedance of medium A and medium B, respectively.

Considering an ultrasonic signal transmitted from a PVC pipe ($Z = 3.27 \cdot 10^6$ Rayls) to air under standard conditions ($Z = 340$ Rayls), the energy transmission coefficient is only 0.042 %. For this reason, clamp-on sensors developed for gas applications often require gas pressures of several bar to achieve sufficient coupling. This drawback makes the clamp-on configuration unsuitable for the application discussed in this work; therefore, the inline configuration was preferred.

2.3.2 Housing Design

The geometry of the sensor directly affects the measurements. For a given volumetric flow rate, modifying the cross-sectional area A changes the flow velocity v . As shown in Equations 2.1 and 2.2, increasing the flow velocity results in a larger contribution to the measured term, which leads to higher accuracy, particularly at low flow rates. At the same time, changing A also affects the distance between the transducers L , whose reduction decreases the minimum measurable Δ_{TOF} .

To increase L without increasing the cross-sectional area A , it is possible to vary the incidence angle θ or to modify the ultrasonic path. There exist configurations in which the signal reflects off the pipe walls or off surfaces placed within the fluid; these configurations are referred to as H, V or W depending on the transducer arrangement. Although such solutions offer theoretical advantages, they also introduce additional complexity: the choice of housing material becomes critical to ensure high signal reflectivity at the walls. Additionally, a longer path increases the sensor accuracy, but attenuation of the signal increases as well. For this reason, the simplest configuration was adopted, which is commonly called Z configuration, in which the transducers face each other.

The incidence angle θ influences both the distance between the transducers and the dimensions of the cavity in front of the transducer face; its effect was studied during the design iterations, by reducing the cavity volume, the measurement error is reduced. To minimize pressure drop between the pipe and the sensor, the cross-section is circular and has the same diameter as the pipe. To avoid turbulence, the opening for the temperature sensor is located downstream of the transducers. The connection between the sensor and the pipes is sealed with PTFE tape, while the transducer and temperature sensor cavities are sealed using O-rings. The sensor housing is manufactured using SLA printing, a technique that ensures airtight components.

The design iterations were evaluated by observing the Δ_{TOF} at different volumetric flow rates. The selected design is the one showing the lowest standard deviation and the closest agreement with the expected theoretical value; Table 2.5 summarizes the design iterations, while Figure 2.7 shows the selected design.

Table 2.5. Design iterations

Iteration	Pipe diameter (in)	Angle (deg)	Length (mm)
1	1/2	45	90
2	1/2	45	120
3	1/2	60	120
4	3/4	60	120

Figure 2.7. Rendering of sensor housing. Transducers (a) and temperature sensor (b) are highlighted.

2.4 Signal Processing

In this section, signal processing is discussed. By filtering the noisy measurements it is possible to significantly decrease the error. A Kalman Filter and a Simple Moving Average are compared. [Chen et al. \(2020\)](#) discusses a filtering algorithm based on the Kalman Filter, which reduced the relative error in the $0.025\text{--}0.4\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$ range from 17.73 % to 1.7 %. In this study, the Kalman Filter performance is compared with a Simple Moving Average.

2.4.1 Kalman Filter

The Kalman filter is used in a wide range of applications, for example in the planning and navigation of robots and vehicles. It is also employed in time-series analysis, as in the present case. Due to its nature, the Kalman Filter reacts faster than a moving average to sudden state changes, therefore it is well suited for applications where the state is expected to change frequently and suddenly during the measuring period. The algorithm is divided into two phases: prediction and update. During the prediction phase, the state variables are estimated, while in the update phase these estimates are corrected through a weighted average that includes the current measurement. The system is described by the following model:

$$x_k = Ax_{k-1} + Bu_k + w_k \quad (2.13)$$

$$z_k = Cx_k + v_k \quad (2.14)$$

where x_k is the state vector, u_k the input, z_k the measurement, and w_k and v_k are Gaussian noises with distributions $w_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q_k)$ and $v_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R_k)$. Since the process has no inputs, $u_k = 0$.

During the prediction step, the state at the next iteration is predicted and the covariance matrix is updated:

$$\hat{x}_{k|k-1} = A\hat{x}_{k-1|k-1} \quad (2.15)$$

$$P_{k|k-1} = AP_{k-1|k-1}A^T + Q_k \quad (2.16)$$

During the update step, the new measurement is compared with the predicted state. When the covariance $P_{k|k-1}$ is large, the Kalman gain K_k approaches unity, so that the measurement is weighted more heavily than the prior estimate:

$$K_k = P_{k|k-1}C^T[CP_{k|k-1}C^T + R_k]^{-1} \quad (2.17)$$

$$\hat{x}_{k|k} = [I - K_kC]\hat{x}_{k|k-1} + K_kz_k \quad (2.18)$$

$$P_{k|k} = [I - K_kC]P_{k|k-1} \quad (2.19)$$

The filter is applied to both transit-time measurements. The state is assumed constant over time ($A = 1$) and the measurement model is $z_k = x_k + v_k$, meaning that $C = 1$. The noise covariances R and Q are determined empirically.

2.4.2 Simple Moving Average

A simple moving average is commonly used to smooth noisy data. This filter computes the average of a window that is shifted over the measurements, a larger window size provides a smoother line, but reacts more slowly to state changes. A simple moving average performs best when a steady state is expected. A comparison between filtered and raw data at zero flow is provided in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8. Comparison between raw and filtered data.

The application considered in this study consists in long measurement periods, where the state is expected to be mainly steady. As demonstrated in Figure 2.8, the Simple Moving Average with a window size of 15 samples returns a slightly lower standard deviation than the Kalman Filter and is therefore the preferred filtering method for the rest of the study.

Additional filtering is required for $\text{CH}_4 - \text{CO}_2$ gas mixture. The threshold detect comparator should trigger for the same lobe on both directions, this is not trivial as signal paths are not perfectly symmetrical and echo signal amplitude on the two sides is not exactly equal. Selecting parameters that offer a robust same lobe detection is challenging when echo signals have varying amplitude, as in this case, where higher CO_2 concentration reduces wave amplitude. During data processing, measurements that considered different lobes are removed.

2.5 Calibration Procedure

Calibration was conducted under operating conditions representative of field use. Domestic biogas stoves typically consume approximately 300–400 L/h of biogas (Kurchania *et al.*, 2011; Tilley *et al.*, 2014), corresponding to about 5.0–6.7 L min^{-1} . Moreover, methane content in biogas generally ranges between 49.5% and 70.5% (Li *et al.*, 2019). To encompass these conditions and provide operational margin, the sensor was calibrated over a volumetric flow range of 2–10 L min^{-1} using $\text{CH}_4 - \text{CO}_2$ gas mixtures with methane concentrations between 40% and 100%. Calibration was performed at room temperature ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$). Reference flow rate and gas composition were provided by a Bronkhorst mass flow controller. To ensure a fully de-

veloped flow profile at the measurement section, straight pipe lengths of $20D$ upstream and $10D$ downstream of the sensor were used. To identify suitable AFE configuration parameters while minimizing test gas consumption, initial calibration was performed using ambient air. The parameters were subsequently refined using $\text{CH}_4\text{-CO}_2$ gas mixtures.

2.5.1 Calibration Function

During calibration with air, volumetric flow rates between 2 and 10 L min^{-1} were applied in increments of 2 L min^{-1} . At each flow rate, one measurement was recorded every two seconds, yielding a total of 100 measurements per step. For calibration with $\text{CH}_4\text{-CO}_2$ mixtures, 50 measurements per flow step were recorded and two measurement runs were performed for each concentration. The methane concentration ranged between 40% and 100% in increments of 10%. For each gas composition, the expected speed of sound c was computed using the CoolProp library. During operation, the sensor measures the transit time in both directions and computes the speed of sound c and the volumetric flow rate Q using Equations 2.4 and 2.5. Systematic deviations between measured and expected values were observed and attributed to electronic offsets and flow–structure interactions within the sensor housing.

To compensate for these effects, a quadratic calibration function was applied to Q and c :

$$x_{\text{cal}} = \alpha x_{\text{meas}}^2 + \beta x_{\text{meas}} + \gamma \quad (2.20)$$

where x_{cal} is the calibrated value, x_{meas} is the measured value, and α , β , and γ are regression coefficients.

The regression coefficients were obtained by comparing measured and expected values at each calibration step, the coefficients are provided in Table A.3. To exclude transient effects introduced by step changes of the mass flow controller, only the final 50 % of the measurements at each step were used for calibration.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results obtained under the operating conditions defined in Section 2.5.1. The dataset used for calibration is also employed for performance evaluation, as the objective is to assess the achievable accuracy of the calibrated sensor under controlled and repeatable conditions. All measurements were performed at room temperature, using reference values provided by a mass flow controller.

3.1 Error Analysis

Sensor performance is evaluated using the **Relative Root Mean Square Error (RRMSE)**, defined as the root mean square error normalized by the mean of the reference values:

$$\text{RRMSE} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i} \quad (3.1)$$

where y_i denotes the reference value, \hat{y}_i the measured value, and n the number of samples. Error analysis results are presented separately for air and for CH₄-CO₂ mixtures in the following subsections.

3.1.1 Air Error Analysis

The analysis of air flow rate measurements serves to validate the sensor and to enable comparison with reference values reported in the literature. Figure 3.1 shows the **RRMSE** and the corresponding 95 % confidence intervals for flow rates between 2 and 10 L min⁻¹.

The mean error at 2 L min⁻¹ is slightly higher than at larger flow rates, where it remains between 0.5 and 1.5 %. Comparable results are reported in the literature. For example, [Chen et al. \(2020\)](#) reports an error of 1.67 % at 6.7 L min⁻¹, decreasing to 1.09 % at 26.7 L min⁻¹, while [Oya et al. \(2022\)](#) reports an error of 2.04 % at 0.67 L min⁻¹, decreasing to 0.33 % at 24 L min⁻¹. Considering the zero-flow Δ_{TOF} , which is theoretically expected to be zero, the error obtained in this study is ± 1.5 ns, as reported in Section 2.4.2, whereas [Oya et al. \(2022\)](#)

Figure 3.1. Mean RRMSE for air flow rate.

and [Chen *et al.* \(2020\)](#) report values of ± 0.7 and ± 4 ns, respectively.

This analysis indicates that an error below 3 % can be achieved within the investigated flow range.

3.1.2 CH₄ – CO₂ Mixture Error Analysis

The flow rate error for the CH₄–CO₂ mixture is analyzed both by using an individual calibration function for each concentration, as shown in [Figure 3.2](#), and by using a single calibration function based on the complete dataset, as presented in [Figure 3.3a](#).

Considering the first approach ([Figure 3.2](#)), the trend observed for air measurements is confirmed: the error decreases as the volumetric flow rate increases. At a given volumetric flow rate, the error increases with increasing CO₂ concentration. This behavior can be attributed to increased ultrasonic attenuation at higher CO₂ concentrations, which reduces the amplitude of the received signal and consequently lowers the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Since the TDC-based method relies on signal magnitude for STOP signal generation, reduced signal amplitude increases the likelihood that triggering occurs on different lobes of the received waveform. A parameter selection that is robust for a given concentration is not necessarily equally robust when the mixture composition changes, therefore failing to trigger on the expected lobe. Because the signal paths cannot be perfectly symmetric, even when high-quality components are used, triggering may occur on different lobes of the received waveform in the upstream and downstream directions. In this case, the measured time of flight is effectively increased by one

Figure 3.2. Mean RRMSE for volumetric flow of CH₄ – CO₂ mixture, where a calibration function is fitted for each composition.

signal period, corresponding to approximately 2 μs . Measurements exhibiting this behavior are classified as outliers and excluded from the dataset. If this occurs repeatedly, it can lead to the absence of valid measurements at specific operating points, as observed at 2 L min⁻¹ and 80 % CH₄ concentration (missing blue marker).

Figure 3.3. Mean RRMSE for volumetric flow and composition.

Using a single calibration function independent of gas composition would be desirable from a practical standpoint. In principle, this should be feasible, as Equation 2.3 does not explicitly depend on gas composition. However, as shown in Figure 3.3a, the resulting mean error is higher at all considered volumetric flow rates, reaching an average value of approximately

130 % at 2 L min^{-1} and settling between 15 and 32 % at higher flow rates. The uncertainty introduced by signal attenuation prevents the identification of a single calibration function capable of accurately calibrating the sensor.

The composition error, shown in Figure 3.3b, is also obtained using a single calibration function. As the volumetric flow rate increases, the composition error remains approximately constant for mixtures containing 70 % and 100 % methane, while it increases for concentrations of 80 % and 90 %. The composition error ranges between 0.8 –1.2 % and is significantly lower than the volumetric flow rate error. This difference arises because the two quantities operate on different orders of magnitude: a timing error of 20 ns corresponds to approximately 2 L min^{-1} in volumetric flow rate, but only to an error on the order of $1e^{-4}$ % in composition.

The composition range considered in this analysis is limited to methane concentrations between 70 % and 100 %. Below 70 % CH_4 , measurements become increasingly unreliable due to severe signal attenuation. At 60 % methane concentration, even with maximum amplification and the most sensitive threshold settings, triggering predominantly occurs on different waveform lobes in the two propagation directions. At lower concentrations, the received signal is no longer distinguishable from noise.

Overall, these results indicate that while accurate flow and composition measurements are achievable at high methane concentrations, increasing CO_2 content rapidly degrades measurement reliability due to signal attenuation and lobe ambiguity, representing the primary limitation of the proposed sensor architecture.

3.2 Production Cost

This study focuses on keeping the cost of the sensors as low as possible. Assuming a production volume of 100 units, the estimated cost breakdown per sensor is reported in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Estimated production cost breakdown per sensor for a batch of 100 units.

Component	Cost (CHF)
SLA Printed Housing	9.58
ESP32 DevKitC	8
PCB	7.03
500 kHz transducers	7.00
PT500 Temperature sensor	2.10
Wiring	1.90
Fastening and sealing	0.13
Total	35.74

Further cost reductions could be achieved by modifying the manufacturing process of the

sensor housing, which is currently produced using SLA printing. Switching to injection molding would substantially reduce the unit cost; however, the upfront cost of mold fabrication makes this option economically viable only for production volumes of several thousand units. Additional cost savings could be obtained by modifying the printed circuit board design, for instance by directly integrating the ESP32 instead of using a socketed development module.

The resulting unit cost is well below the constraint defined in the research question. Moreover, it is significantly lower than that of commercial ultrasonic flow meters, which often exceed 1000 CHF, and is comparable to low-cost solutions such as the UFM-01 produced by ScioSense.

3.3 Future Work

The use of transit-time ultrasonic flow meters in applications with high CO₂ concentrations remains challenging. While such measurements are technically feasible, as demonstrated by high-end commercial sensors, the primary difficulty lies in achieving comparable performance at low-cost. To mitigate ultrasonic signal attenuation, two main approaches can be considered: increasing the transmitted acoustic power or improving the extraction of the received signal under low-SNR conditions. Increasing the transmitted acoustic power can be achieved by raising the excitation voltage. However, this would require transducers with higher voltage ratings and more powerful driver circuits, leading to increased cost and potential safety concerns associated with operating at elevated voltages in proximity to flammable gases. An alternative approach involves the use of transducers specifically designed to enhance the acoustic transmission coefficient, such as those employed in the FLOWSIC600 ultrasonic flow sensor (Harper *et al.*, 2009). Since these transducers are custom components, their use would likely result in substantially higher production costs.

Focusing on the reception side, a promising direction is the adoption of an ADC-based approach, as implemented in the MSP430FR6043 by Texas Instruments. Although this device is slightly more expensive than the solution used in this work, the ADC-based method enables more robust signal processing under low-SNR conditions. This solution addresses the two main challenges encountered in this work. An envelope is extracted from the sampled analog signal, the triggering threshold is then defined as a percentage of the envelope maximum, thereby reducing sensitivity to absolute signal amplitude. In addition, the device employs a cascaded integrator–comb filter, which provides more effective attenuation of high-frequency noise than the first-order filters implemented in this study. For these reasons, this approach represents a promising direction for future work and should be evaluated prior to more costly or complex alternatives.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This thesis presents the development of a low-cost transit-time ultrasonic flow meter targeting biogas applications. The design process prioritized cost minimization while maintaining acceptable measurement accuracy, resulting in a prototype with an estimated unit cost of approximately 36 CHF.

For air volumetric flow measurements, the sensor achieves a mean relative error below 3 % over the range from 2 to 10 Lmin⁻¹. When operated with biogas-like CH₄-CO₂ mixtures containing methane concentrations between 70 and 100 %, the sensor is able to estimate gas composition with a mean relative error below 1 %. In contrast, the mean flow rate error under these conditions is significantly higher, ranging from approximately 15 to 160 %, depending on flow rate. This degradation in performance is attributed to the strong attenuation of ultrasonic signals in CO₂-rich mixtures, which leads to a reduced signal-to-noise ratio and limits the robustness of time-of-flight detection.

For methane concentrations below 70 %, the current prototype is unable to reliably measure either volumetric flow rate or gas composition, as signal attenuation becomes too severe for the adopted measurement approach. While this limitation restricts the operational range of the present design, the results provide valuable insight into the constraints of low-cost transit-time ultrasonic sensing in highly attenuating gas mixtures.

Based on the experience gained in this work, several directions for future development can be identified. In particular, the adoption of an [ADC](#)-based timing approach could significantly improve measurement robustness in CO₂-rich environments by enabling more advanced signal extraction techniques that remain effective under low [SNR](#) conditions. Such an approach represents a promising pathway toward extending the applicability of low-cost ultrasonic flow meters to a broader range of biogas compositions.

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APPENDIX A - ADDITIONAL DATA

A.1 TDC1000 & TDC7200 Register Configurations

Table A.1. TDC1000 register configuration.

address	register	bit fields	configured function
0x00	CONFIG_0	100 00101	TX_FREQ_DIV = 4 (divide by 32); NUM_TX = 5 pulses
0x01	CONFIG_1	01 000 001	reserved = 01; NUM_AVG = 0 (1 cycle); NUM_RX = 1 event
0x02	CONFIG_2	0 0 1 0 0 0 01	VCOM internal; TOF measure- ment (not temperature); damping enabled; no channel swap; exter- nal CHSEL disabled; channel 1; TOF mode 1
0x03	CONFIG_3	0 1 1 0 1 010	TEMP_MODE = REF+RTD1; RTD type = PT500; TEMP clock divide- by-8; power blanking enabled; echo threshold = 2 (-75 mV)
0x05	TOF_1	100 0 0 1 00	PGA gain = 12 dB; PGA active; LNA active; resistive feedback; TIMING_REG[9:8] = 0
0x06	TOF_0	00100000	TIMING_REG[7:0] = 32 (TIM- ING_REG = 32 total)
0x08	TIMEOUT	0 0 000 0 10	force short-TOF disabled; short- TOF blank = $8 \times T_0$; echo timeout enabled; listen window = $512 \times T_0$
0x09	CLOCK_RATE	00000 1 10	CLKIN divided by 2 (sets T_0); auto-zero period = $256 \times T_0$

Table A.2. TDC7200 register configuration.

address	register	bit fields	configured function
0x00	CONFIG1	0 1 0 0 0 01 0	FORCE_CAL=0; parity enabled; TRIGG/START/STOP on rising edge; measurement mode 2; START_MEAS=0
0x01	CONFIG2	01 000 000	calibration2 uses 10 clock periods; averaging disabled (1 cycle); single STOP

A.2 Sensor Flowchart

Figure A.1. Flowchart demonstrating the processes and decision that are executed by the sensor. pink boxes performed by MCU, green boxes performed by TDC7200, blue boxes performed by TDC1000.

A.3 Regression Coefficients

In this section the obtained regression coefficients calibration functions are provided.

Table A.3. Regression coefficients for calibration function.

Application	α	β	γ
Air flow rate	0.0263	1.0195	-1.5566
CH ₄ – CO ₂ flow rate	0.0107	0.6421	2.4848
CH ₄ – CO ₂ composition	0	0.8431	61.3183

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